

Supplemental Table 1 (S1)

Collection state and region for specimens (N = number of specimens) analyzed for *T. cruzi* infection grouped based on order and species (vector) or number of species (Hg = haplogroup).

State	Region	Order	Species	N
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Artiodactyla	4 species	197
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Carnivora (companion)	2 species	186
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Chiroptera	9 species	159
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Didelphimorphia	3 species	15
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> complex	42
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg1	13
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg2	9
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Perissodactyla	1 species	4
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Primates	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	92
Campeche	Zoh Laguna	Rodentia	7 species	129
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Artiodactyla	3 species	20
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Carnivora (companion)	2 species	68
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Chiroptera	11 species	67
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Didelphimorphia	3 species	18
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> complex	63
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg1	5
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg2	235
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg3	25
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Perissodactyla	3 species	22
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Primates	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	14
Chiapas	Berriozabal	Rodentia	4 species	183
Chiapas	Palenque	Chiroptera	9 species	42
Chiapas	Palenque	Didelphimorphia	2 species	7
Chiapas	Palenque	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg1	20
Chiapas	Palenque	Hemiptera	<i>P. rufotuberculatus</i>	3
Chiapas	Palenque	Rodentia	3 species	32
Chiapas	Tapachula	Chiroptera	5 species	91
Chiapas	Tapachula	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg3	16
Morelos	Domestic	Hemiptera	<i>T. pallidipennis</i>	61
Morelos	Landscapes	Artiodactyla	1 species	12
Morelos	Landscapes	Carnivora (companion)	2 species	4

Morelos	Landscapes	Carnivora (wildlife)	<i>2 species</i>	9
Morelos	Landscapes	Chiroptera	<i>22 species</i>	501
Morelos	Landscapes	Didelphimorphia	<i>2 species</i>	7
Morelos	Landscapes	Hemiptera	<i>T. pallidipennis</i>	199
Morelos	Landscapes	Lagomorpha	<i>1 species</i>	5
Morelos	Landscapes	Rodentia	<i>13 species</i>	231
Oaxaca	Nopala	Chiroptera	<i>8 species</i>	24
Oaxaca	Nopala	Primates	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	15
Oaxaca	Salina Cruz	Hemiptera	<i>T. phyllosoma</i>	59
Oaxaca	Salina Cruz	Primates	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	18
Oaxaca	Valles	Hemiptera	<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg2	64